

2022 Vocabulary Symposium and Workshop Report

Contributors

Megan Wong, Rowan Brownlee, Lesley Wyborn, Melanie Barlow, Kheeran Dharmawardena, Natalia Atkins, Simon Cox.

Summary

Event organisers

[Organisational Partners](#)

[Organising Committee](#)

2022 Vocabulary Symposium purpose

[How did people attend the Symposium?](#)

[Who attended the Symposium?](#)

[What topics were covered by the Symposium presentations?](#)

[Symposium keynotes.](#)

[Feedback from Symposium participants \(via Menti\)](#)

2022 Vocabulary Workshop purpose.

[Workshop participants](#)

[Workshop activities and outputs](#)

[Day 1: Context Setting and Mapping the Landscape](#)

[Day 1, group activity 1 Feedback on questions](#)

[Day 1, group activity 2. Identifying infrastructure](#)

[Day 1, group activity 3. identifying vocabularies used within and across domains](#)

[Day 2: Guidance and governance of cross-domain vocabularies](#)

[Group discussions were aimed at informing roadmap planning for day 3](#)

[Day 2. Activity 1. Mapping the Landscape - documents, legislation, guidelines, groups, reviews etc that could support or constrain](#)

[Day 2. Activity 2. Cross-domain scenario](#)

[Day 2. Activity 3. Stakeholder scoping](#)

[Day 2. Activity 4. Beginning to plan a Roadmap](#)

[DAY 3: The Path Forward \(Friday, half-day\)](#)

[Day 3. Continuing the Roadmap discussion and a strategy for taking the roadmap forward](#)

Recommendations

Links to resources

[Appendix for Day 2, Activity 1 - Mapping the Landscape Documents](#)

Summary

An open-access Symposium on FAIR vocabularies across domains, followed by an invitation-only Workshop on vocabulary service development were held at the Australian National University (ANU), Canberra during November 2022.

The purpose of the Symposium was to bring together users, creators and publishers of [vocabularies](#) across domains and sectors in Australia, to share experiences and identify requirements for FAIR vocabularies underpinning cross-domain data.

Held [online and in person](#), on November 14 and 15, 2022, the Symposium was headlined by plenary presentations on the future of vocabulary management, within and across domains. It provided opportunities for participants to

- hear about cross-domain vocabularies in practice, and strategies for managing and governing vocabularies;
- meet experts and make new connections, and join the community of people who are working with vocabularies and vocabulary services; and
- contribute to addressing social, institutional and ecosystem challenges and opportunities in adoption and management of vocabularies.

The [workshop](#) was an invitation-only in-person event held on November 16-18, 2022, which focused on developing a program for how to promote movement from the current state of Australian vocabularies toward a future state that meets next generation vocabulary requirements (FAIR and well governed). The Workshop was oriented around these questions:

- What is our current vocabulary landscape and what does it need to look like in the future?
- What would constitute an optimum future state?
- How may we work towards a future state?
- What do we need to do in order to harmonise and converge our thinking?
- How might we achieve sustainability and longevity of the critical services within the vocabulary landscape so that these will be there in 10 years time?

Event organisers

The Symposium and Workshop were held in partnership between ADA, ARDC and CODATA.

Organisational Partners

- Australian Data Archive (ADA), represented by Steve McEachern
- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), represented by Adrian Burton
- CODATA (Committee on Data of the International Science Council), represented by Simon Hodson

Organising Committee

- Rowan Brownlee - ARDC
- Simon Cox - CSIRO Environmental Informatics, CODATA
- Kheeran Dharmawardena - Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water and Cytrax
- Steve McEachern - Australian Data Archive, Australian National University, DDI
- Megan Wong - Federation University Centre of eResearch and Digital Innovation (CeRDI)
- Lesley Wyborn - ARDC, NCI, AuScope

2022 Vocabulary Symposium purpose

The [Vocabulary Symposium](#) was held on 14 to 15 November 2022 online and in person at the Research School of Social Sciences of the Australian National University (ANU). It brought together more than 200 users, creators and publishers of vocabularies across domains and sectors in Australia and Internationally. Featuring examples of how vocabularies were being used within and across domains, participants shared experiences and identified requirements for FAIR vocabularies underpinning cross-domain data.

How did people attend the Symposium?

There were 59 onsite registrations, and 181 online registrations.

Who attended the Symposium?

There were a mix of participants from universities and other research organisations, cultural heritage institutions, [NCRIS](#) facilities, state and federal government. Domains included science, health & medicine, indigenous, social sciences, earth & environmental, humanities and arts. Participants attended from Australia, New Zealand, Japan, Iraq, Spain, Italy, Indonesia, Ireland, Slovenia, Finland, France, Germany, Israel, India, Canada, and USA.

The graphs below relate to the following roles:

- “Registered Person” - person who registered to attend the Symposium via EventBrite (Figure 1);
- Webinar Participant” - person who connected to the Zoom Webinar (Figure 2); and
- “Attendee” - person who responded to a menti survey (online or offline) (Figure 3).

Registered Person Email Domain

Figure 1: “Registered Person Email Domain” - From EventBrite registration data (Organisation Name was not required by EventBrite at time of registration, so could not be used in preference to email domain. Note that a person may have registered with a gmail account even though they are employed at somewhere other than google).

Registered Person - Online/In-Person

Figure 2: “Registered Person Online/In-Person” - From EventBrite registration data.

Attendee Sector

Figure 3: “Attendee Sector” - Results of Menti survey (attendee may have been either online or offline).

Attendee Domain

Figure 4: “Attendee Domain” - Results of Menti survey (attendee may have been either online or offline).

Webinar Participant Country - 14 November

Figure 5: “Webinar Participant Country 14 November” - From Zoom Webinar connection data.

Webinar Participant Country - 15 November

Figure 6: “Webinar Participant Country - 15 November” - From Zoom Webinar connection data.

What topics were covered by the Symposium presentations?

Presentation slides and recordings are linked from the [Symposium program](#). There were two keynote presentations (one online, one onsite) and 17 session presentations (11 online, 6 onsite).

There were three areas into which the presentations were grouped:

- International Vocabularies and services;
- Current practices concerning vocabularies in Australia; and
- Systems and tools for discovering and reusing vocabularies.

Within those groupings presentations covered areas such as:

- Vocabularies that are used across domains;
- Interoperability frameworks enabling the application of vocabularies across domains;
- An approach to managing vocabularies using tools originating from software development;
- Challenges involved in managing vocabularies that are used by different groups - bringing those groups together;
- The importance of inclusion in vocabulary development, of engaging with user groups;
- Systems and tools for publication and access;
- Finding, managing and reusing vocabularies; and
- Vocabulary governance.

Symposium keynotes.

Simon Hodson (CODATA) and Adrian Burton (ARDC) delivered the plenary presentations,

Simon discussed CODATA's longstanding involvement supporting and promoting good governance & sustainability in vocabulary development. And he gave an overview of a range of current initiatives concerning interoperability across domains. In particular the Global Open Science Cloud and WorldFAIR Projects and the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs).

Adrian discussed ARDC strategies and services for developing knowledge infrastructure for impactful research. ARDC provides, supports and promotes a range of services around catalogues, persistent identifiers and vocabularies that are aimed at making, discovering and reusing data connections across organisations & sectors, spanning inputs, activities & outputs. The objective is to allow our researchers to address society's grand challenges through deeper insights from larger, joined up pools of data as well as through novel insights from disparate data.

Feedback from Symposium participants (via Menti)

We asked what types of vocabularies participants mainly work with. As illustrated in Figure 7 modified from e Obrst¹, there were at least two substantial groups, with an additional 13 responses in the area of simple lists, and 16 responses around RDF & conceptual models.

Figure 7: Plot of where attendees nominated which types of vocabularies they were mainly working on the Ontology Spectrum of Obrst.

We asked how the participants would describe the current vocabulary landscape in Australia. The greatest number of responses mentioned terms such as “emerging, fragmented, evolving and confusing”.

We asked participants to identify challenges in meeting vocabulary needs. Responses identified issues concerning technology, skills, governance and standards.

When asked to identify gaps in the 2022 Australian vocabulary landscape, responses included governance, mappings, persistent identifiers, coordination and funding. [Discussion notes](#) from a group brainstorm session are available.

¹ Obrst in Davis, M.: Semantic Wave 2008 Report: Industry Roadmap to Web 3.0 & Multibillion Dollar Market Opportunities (2008), <http://www.project10x.com> Report accessed from <https://www.scribd.com/document/2599547/Project10X-s-Semantic-Wave-2008-Report-Industry-Roadmap-to-Web-3-0> on 20 June, 2023

2022 Vocabulary Workshop purpose.

The [Vocabulary Workshop](#) was held between November 16 - 18 2022, at the Research School of Social Sciences, Australian National University, Canberra. The workshop aimed to take first steps in developing a program for how we move from the current state of Australian vocabularies toward a future state that meets next generation vocabulary requirements (FAIR and well governed).

The following questions offered starting points for discussion across the event

- What is our current vocabulary landscape and what does it need to look like in the future?
- What would constitute an optimum future state?
- How may we work towards a future state?
- What do we need to do in order to harmonise and converge our thinking?
- How might we achieve sustainability and longevity of the critical services within the vocabulary landscape so that these will be there in 10 years time?

Workshop participants

Participation was by invitation, with invitees identified as vocabulary creators, managers, service/tooling providers or advocates within and across domains including health & medicine, earth and environmental science, humanities, arts, social sciences and indigenous. This included participants working across these domains in technology and services provision, including in the geospatial domain. Particular focus was placed upon domains covered by the [CODATA WorldFAIR](#) and [ARDC Thematic Research Data Commons](#) initiatives.

The research, government and industry sectors were all represented and participants were from Agencies and Organisations including Research (Federal, State and or Territorial, Universities), National Data Infrastructures (Including NCRIS Facilities), consultants and service providers (see attendee sector figure)

Workshop activities and outputs

Day 1: Context Setting and Mapping the Landscape

Day One focused upon collectively mapping the Australian vocabulary landscape, and connections with international initiatives. To identify what is available now, and to help participants think about future needs, such as services & infrastructure, relationships, domain and generic vocabularies, and communities.

Presentations from [Adrian Burton \(ARDC\)](#) and [Andrew Hancock \(StatsNZ, Tauranga Aotearoa\)](#), set the scene. Adrian introduced the ARDC Thematic Research Data Commons and

ARDC Services. Andrew discussed NZ and international initiatives to modernise management of statistical classifications. There were also a series of brief [presentations](#) on communities and initiatives relating to vocabularies.

Across day one, group activities were organised through a series of sessions. Participants worked in domain groups. These included health & medicine, earth and environmental science, humanities, arts, social sciences and indigenous, as well as cross-domain areas such as geospatial.

Day 1, group activity 1 Feedback on questions

One of the group activities involved reviewing and reporting back upon the responses to questions that were posed at a [2022 eResearch Australasia BoF](#) session, and during the preceding [Symposium](#).

- Where are Australians utilising International Vocabulary resources?
- When should we have local, national vs international. Is there consensus?

Although there was considerable discussion, no notes were recorded.

Day 1, group activity 2. Identifying infrastructure

Another group activity had participants identifying infrastructure, services and resources.

Questions such as

- What are the vocabulary repositories, portals, aggregators
- What are the systems for editing and managing vocabularies
- Are they sustainable & FAIR?
- Are there connections with international equivalents?
- Are there gaps compared to overseas initiatives?

Known repositories include:

- RVA, Geoscience Australia, BoM, TERN, Department of Finance, ABS, AIHW (Meteor), Archives, GSQ.

Known portals include:

- ARDC-RVA, Ontoserver, GSQ, GA, TERN, HASS, National Archives, ABS, National Library, ABIS.

Known resources for editing and managing vocabularies include

- PoolParty, Excel/SKOS-Play!, Excel/VocPrez, RDF tools (TopBraid, Protege)².

² The 2021 workshop produced a [draft list of tools](#).

Day 1, group activity 3. identifying vocabularies used within and across domains

Across the workshop, participants were asked to review and add to a [list of vocabularies](#)³ used within their domain, and across domains. To support post-workshop discussion of questions such as

- Which vocabularies are required across domains?
- Which vocabularies are domain-specific but are needed by other domains?
- How might guidance on vocabulary selection be provided?
- What to do about multiple copies of similar vocabularies?

Day 2: Guidance and governance of cross-domain vocabularies

Group discussions were aimed at informing roadmap planning for day 3

Day 2. Activity 1. Mapping the Landscape - documents, legislation, guidelines, groups, reviews etc that could support or constrain

As a group activity, participants were presented with sources of information intended to stimulate thinking around development of a vision and roadmap. These included documents, and descriptions of interest groups & communities of practice focusing upon vocabularies.⁴ Participants suggested other documents and groups to be added to a consolidated set of information resources.⁵

Participants felt that all of the documents, initiatives and or directives identified are likely to support rather than constrain the creation and use of vocabularies for FAIR data. Some may also inform how vocabularies are governed and managed for best practice of equity and transparency, such as Codes of Ethics and [Commonwealth DATA legislation](#).

Day 2. Activity 2. Cross-domain scenario

Participants were organised into cross-domain groups to work on a scenario

What are the environmental, economic and social determinants of a new disease? (e.g., mapping the spread of a new disease in northern Australia).

The groups were tasked with identifying and reporting back on two questions

1. Which vocabularies and datasets would be required to assist with tackling this scenario?
2. What were the main barriers to linking these vocabularies and datasets across infrastructures?

A joint discussion followed on the barriers to interdisciplinary integration of vocabularies in Australia. Notes from two of the breakout sessions were recorded [here](#) and [here](#). [Link to slides](#)

³ Note that the list is not intended to be comprehensive, but to support discussion

⁴ See [appendix](#) for information presented to participants

⁵ See [appendix](#) for information added by participants

Session 10: Cross-domain scenario Part 1

NEWS FLASH

A new virus has been discovered in northern Australia that is causing severe illness and death in people. It is spreading fast amongst the population and there is a suspicion that it is transmitted from air and possibly via animal vectors.

We are the cross discipline panel of experts here to save the country (and maybe the world) from imminent doom!

We need to provide advice on what the environmental, economic and social determinants of this new disease is

- 1) Which vocabularies would be required to assist in this scenario?
- 2) What are the barriers to linking these across infrastructures - are they domain, technical, sector, social or governance?

Day 2. Activity 3. Stakeholder scoping

During this session the extended enterprise architecture model was used to develop a supply chain view of vocabularies and create a holistic view of the relationships with vocabulary suppliers, consumers (customers), and other stakeholders in the value chain.

Intention was for the workshop participants to gain understanding and insights into the interactions among suppliers, supplier's suppliers, customers, and customer's customers as they started to synthesis a roadmap for vocabularies in Australia.

During this session, the extended enterprise architecture model was employed as a framework to construct a comprehensive supply chain perspective on vocabularies, fostering a holistic understanding of the relationships between vocabulary suppliers, consumers (customers), and other stakeholders involved in the value chain.

The primary objective of the session was to facilitate participants in gaining valuable insights and comprehension of the complex interactions among suppliers, supplier's suppliers, customers, and customer's customers.

vocabulary supply chain. The focus of these discussions centred primarily on the relationships between suppliers and customers, as well as suppliers and their respective supplier's suppliers.

Participants recognized the unique dynamic wherein many customers also served as suppliers of vocabularies, highlighting the interconnected nature of the vocabulary ecosystem. Additionally, conversations delved into the distinction between knowledge holders (those possessing subject matter expertise) and knowledge coders (those responsible for translating that expertise into structured vocabularies).

This valuable exchange of ideas and insights allowed participants to better understand some of the intricacies of the vocabulary supply chain and the various stakeholder relationships within it, paving the potential for further examination and collaboration in future discussions.

Day 2. Activity 4. Beginning to plan a Roadmap

Although scheduled for day 3, participants began discussions early, toward the latter part of day 2. Canvassing views and approaches, identifying key components and [starting to sketch an outline](#).

INFRASTRUCTURE/ TECHNOLOGY/SKILLS

Flexible mapping of vocabulary terms by
- Providers
- Community

clear linkages between vocabs

PIDs for terms / classifications / hierarchies / lists / vocabs

Seamless handling of lists, vocabs, ontologies in different formats

Vocabulary bindings in Python, R, Java, ...

POINT OF PRESENCE FOR VOCAB
- SEARCH
- DEVELOPMENT
- CURATION
- MAPPING

Who is doing/building equivalent Ecosystem and how do I link to those via machine to machine interfaces.

Service development

API(s)

Tech
- Maintainability
- Easy Access
- FAIR*

VOCAB Development Skills

Federated discovery across vocabulary catalogues

Persistence
(compound) Search for terms in any vocab

Version history and unapping

TOOLS FOR VOCAB DEMOCRATISATION. AUTOMATION. CROSS-DOMAIN

Technology Constraint
- missing APIs (Donald)

POLICY

Sustainable operation of catalogue / services

Policy constraint - classification stability

High impact policies / frameworks
From the trusts

GOVERNANCE + PROGRAM SUPPORT

Content Negotiation by Profile

INVESTMENT PROGRAM MANAGE GOVERNANCE

DAY 3: The Path Forward (Friday, half-day)

Day 3. Continuing the Roadmap discussion and a strategy for taking the roadmap forward

Cross-domain groups began to identify key components of a roadmap and presented back to the larger group.

The final day of the workshop focused on establishing an agenda for next steps.

Participants were interested in :

- developing a road map for a vocabulary ecosystem in Australia
- continuing to work on a draft of a roadmap
- identifying a group to carry forward advocacy of a road map.
- exploring options for communication and awareness-raising, through connections with groups such as [AVSIG](#) and [AGLDWG](#). ([Link to presentation on documents and communities](#))

The day's discussion is reflected in a [draft roadmap document](#)⁶, begun during day 3.

Recommendations

1) Roadmap

At the conclusion of the workshop it was proposed that volunteers from the workshop (comprising vocabulary users, managers and creators from across the multiple domains with independent, yet interconnected, dependencies and who are interested in a trusted, sustainable vocabulary ecosystem in Australia), work to produce a roadmap that articulates a shared vision and path forward for vocabularies in the Australian data ecosystem and society. The purpose of such a roadmap document would be to inform and guide strategy and engagement across areas of industry, academia, and Government including in National Research infrastructure Facilities and Government jurisdictions.

2) Symposium in 2023.

There were suggestions that the Symposium should be run again at the same time of year.

Links to resources

- Symposium presentations (abstracts, slides and recordings) [linked from program](#)
- Workshop presentations from [Adrian Burton \(ARDC\)](#) and [Andrew Hancock \(StatsNZ, Tauranga Aotearoa\)](#)
- Background slides on [starting a roadmap](#).
- Presentations to AVSIG meeting, December 6 2022. Slides and recordings [linked from AVSIG wiki](#)

⁶ This is a very early draft, from the afternoon of November 18, 2022.

Appendix for Day 2, Activity 1 - Mapping the Landscape Documents

Documents provided to participants:

- CODATA Decadal Plan on [Making Data Work for Cross-Domain Grand Challenges: 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#)
- [Australian Learned Academies Data Interworking Network Project](#) (ALADIN) and the 5 reports on Australia's Data-enabled research future
- Australian Academy of Science [Advancing data-intensive research in Australia](#)
- [UN Sustainable Development Goals](#)
- Australian Government Documents:
 - [Australian Data Strategy](#);
 - [Commonwealth DATA legislation](#)
 - [Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022](#)
 - [ONDC Share Data](#)
 - [Foundational Four](#)
 - [Mapping the ONDC and National Archives' metadata requirements | naa.gov.au](#)
- [Australian Code For the Responsible Conduct of Research](#), (in particular the Guide to the [Management of data and information in research](#))
- [RVA review](#)

Documents and initiatives identified by participants:

- International:
 - [UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People](#) (UNDRIP)
 - [The CARE Principles](#)
 - [The TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories](#)
- National:
 - [Auscope - 10 yr strategy](#)
 - [ARC Open access policy](#)
 - [NHMRC open access policy](#)
 - ARDC Institutional Underpinnings Reports:
 - [Research data management framework for institutions](#)
 - [Australia's Research Data Management Framework Projects and Outputs](#)
 - Specifically regarding Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Governance:
 - [National Agreement on closing the gap](#) - priority no 4
 - [Australian Indigenous Data Governance Protocols - Key Principles](#)
 - [AITASIS code of ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research](#)
- Names of interest groups and communities of practice provided to participants:

- [Australian Vocabulary Special Interest Group \(AVSIG\)](#)
- [AGLDWG](#) (Australian Government Linked Data Working Group)
- Research Data Alliance ([RDA](#)) [Vocabulary Services Interest Group](#)
- [Earth Systems Information Partners \(ESIP\) Collaboration Areas:](#)
 - [Semantic Harmonisation Cluster](#)
 - [Schema.org Cluster](#)
 - [Soil Ontology and Informatics Cluster](#)

The participants were asked to identify other groups that should be included to progress development of a shared vision. None were identified.